

TOBACCO PLANT

USES

PAST , PRESENT

AND FUTURE

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Trends in

Bio Science

**Recent Developments and future
prospects in India**

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Dr. Miss. Jyotsna Lal

*Professor in
Chemistry Department*
Christ Church College
affiliated to
C.S.J.M UNIVERSITY
Kanpur . U.P . INDIA

***Nicotiana tabacum*, or cultivated tobacco, is an annually-grown herbaceous plant. It is found only in cultivation, where it is the most commonly grown of all plants in the *Nicotiana* genus, and its leaves are commercially grown in many countries to be processed into tobacco.**

Tobacco farming

TOBACCO USE IN THE PAST

TOBACCO USE IN AYURVEDIC MEDICINE

- Ayurvedic medicine is one of the world's oldest holistic (whole-body) healing systems. It was developed thousands of years ago in India
- Tobacco leaves were made into a syrup with honey was used to treat asthma, chest diseases, cough, and syphilis
- Used as a sedative, diuretic, expectorant, discutient, and sialagogue, The smoke injected into the rectum or the leaf rolled into a suppository has been beneficial in strangulated hernia, also for obstinate constipation, due to spasm of the bowels, also for retention of urine, spasmodic urethral stricture, hysterical convulsions, worms, and in spasms caused by lead, for croup, and inflammation of the peritoneum, to produce evacuation of the bowels, moderating reaction and dispelling tympanitis, and also in tetanus.
- A cataplasm of the leaves may be used as an ointment for cutaneous diseases. The leaves in combination with the leaves of belladonna or stramonium make an excellent application for obstinate ulcers, painful tremors and spasmodic affections.

TOBACCO USE AT PRESENT

- Tobacco is a product prepared from the leaves of the tobacco plant by curing them. The plant is part of the genus *Nicotiana* and of the Solanaceae (nightshade) family. While more than 70 species of tobacco are known, the chief commercial crop is *N. tabacum*. The more potent variant *N. rustica* is also used around the world.
- Tobacco contains the alkaloid nicotine, which is a stimulant. Dried tobacco leaves are mainly used for smoking in cigarettes, cigars, pipe tobacco, and flavored shisha tobacco. They can be also consumed as snuff, chewing tobacco, and dipping tobacco.
- Burning tobacco is the main source of indoor pollution in the developed world..

Tobacco is a risk factor for oral cancer, oral cancer recurrence, adult periodontal diseases and congenital defects such as cleft lip and palate in children. Tobacco suppresses the immune system's response to oral infection, compromises healing following oral surgical and accidental wounding, promotes periodontal degeneration in diabetics and adversely affects the cardiovascular system.

Table TOXIC LEVELS OF NICOTINE

A] Minimum Lethal Dose of Nicotine

Adult Human	40 mg ~0.5- 1.0 mg/kg ;
Topically Child	4mg /kg , Adult 65mg
Human	0.36mg/kg
Cow [1- 1 ½ year old Bulls & Heifer]	> 1 gm
Horse & Cow	200-400 mg
Sheep	100-200 mg
18 month Lambs	200-300 mg
Cat & Dog	20-100 mg
Mouse	40 mg

The WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control, which was adopted in May 2003 by WHO's 192 member States, is intended as a common framework in which countries can work together to address the challenge that tobacco use represents at the global level. In the year 2004 the Central Govt of India passed a legislation on advertisement, production, trade and sale of tobacco and tobacco products .banning the advertisement of tobacco & tobacco products on tv, newspapers and media from 01 may 2004 Reason tobacco leaves contain an alkaloid nicotine which is lethal carcinogen and causes addiction.

FUTURE USE OF TOBACCO PLANT

Tobacco will now be used for manufacturing cancer and cardiac drugs with the Central Tobacco Research Institute (CTRI) bagging the patent for 'solanesol' – a medicinal substance extracted from tobacco.

Solanesol, a white crystalline powder derived from tobacco's green leaf, has curative effects against cardiac insufficiency, muscular dystrophy, anaemia, cancer, diabetes, high blood pressure, asthma and liver injury

The project of deriving solanesol from tobacco was a collaborative programme between CTRI and Central Drug Research Institute (CDRI), Lucknow. CTRI used chewing tobacco variety Abirmanji grown in Tamil Nadu and HDBRG tobacco cultivated in black soils of Guntur in Andhra Pradesh for extracting solanesol

TOBACCO USE IN BIO-PHARMACEUTICALS

- Ebola, is a viral hemorrhagic fever of humans and other primates caused by ebolaviruses. (known as Ebola haemorrhagic fever) is a severe, often fatal but preventable disease. WHO declared Ebola Virus Disease as a public health emergency of international concern, under the International Health Regulations, IHR (2005) on 8 August 2014.

- ZMapp is the drug that saved the lives of American aid workers from Ebola
- ZMapp is manufactured in the tobacco plant *Nicotiana benthamiana* in the bioproduction process known as "pharming" by Kentucky BioProcessing, a subsidiary of Reynolds AmericanKentucky BioProcessing in Owensboro was one of the first biopharmaceutical companies tasked with developing the ZMapp serum through tobacco plants. The company has been working in collaboration with San Diego-based Mapp Biopharmaceutical, which developed the ZMapp vaccine,

- Drugs and vaccines are manufactured in a variety of ways. **Flu vaccines**, for example, are most commonly produced by injecting fertilized hen eggs with the virus. The virus is incubated for days so it can replicate, be harvested, inactivated or weakened, and then made into either a flu shot or nasal spray. The process can cost around \$150 million each year, using \$600,000 eggs each day. Tobacco plants can produce antibodies in much less time for a fraction of the cost, advocates say. The process begins by cloning a gene and inserting it into a virus. That infected gene is then injected into the tobacco plant, where it multiplies within the leaves before it is extracted and purified.

- The northwestern city of Xian is using the counterfeit cigarettes to extract solanesol, a compound found in tobacco which is used to treat cardiovascular disease
- The Canadian biopharmaceutical company PlantForm is using tobacco to produce a drug that reduces the growth rate of breast cancer tumors. The drug is a "biosimilar" form of a current drug on the market called Herceptin, usually produced by creating antibodies in mammalian cells from hamsters' ovaries. The current treatment costs up to \$100,000 per patient, according to PlantForm. The company estimates up to \$120 million could be saved by 2017 by manufacturing the drug with tobacco plants instead

UPCOMING USE OF TOBACCO PLANT

- BIO –FUELS
- PROTEINS
- CARBOXYLIC ACIDS

Application in the Biofuel Industries

Seeds. Tobacco seeds contain high quantities of oil - roughly 40% by weight (19), making them an attractive contender as a source of biofuel (20). However, due to the relatively lower yield of tobacco seeds when compared with other biofuel oil producers like the rapeseeds and soybean, researchers are also looking at modifying tobacco plants to increase the oil content of leaves; this has resulted in about 20-fold more oil in some instances (21) (22). Boeing, South African Airways and SkyNRG have collaborated to manufacture biodiesel from tobacco seed oil - firstly, to reduce aviation fuel price and secondly, to reduce the amount of carbon dioxide released (23).

Plants: The Lignocellulosic biomass from a plant is the most abundantly available raw material for the production of bio-fuels, mainly bio-ethanol (24). Tobacco produces approximately five dry tons of biomass per acre even after removal of potentially useful co-products. This material can be converted to energy or used as a high-nutrition animal feed (25). If converted to ethanol, each acre could produce approximately 335 gallons of ethanol at a rate of 67 gallons/ton of biomass (25).

Tyton BioEnergy Systems is currently working on genetically engineering tobacco plants to increase their sugar and oil content, thus allowing them to be used for both ethanol and biodiesel production (26).

Beyond Nicotine, other substances extractable from Tobacco plants

Carboxylic acids. The major carboxylic acids in tobacco are citric, malic, oxalic and malonic, the composition in total of which can vary from c. 5% to 18% by weight of the plant for different Nicotiana strains and their cultivation conditions (31) (38). Various technologies are being looked at for extraction of these components, particularly citric and malic acids, for their application in the food industry (39) (40).

- Caliber Biotherapeutics applies its expertise in tobacco plant-based expression for manufacturing recombinant proteins targeting non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, multiple myeloma, and breast cancers (15)
- Planet Biotechnology (16) developed CaroRx - an antibody based product for protection against tooth decay - using transgenic tobacco plants. The product is currently undergoing phase 2 clinical trials under a US IND (Investigational New Drug). (17) (18)

Proteins. Tobacco proteins are composed of about 10% Fraction 1 and 90% Fraction 2 proteins (30). They contain a well-balanced amino acids' content and can be crystallized in to a pure powder which has no odour or taste (30). Fraction 1 proteins have been reported to exhibit a higher protein efficiency ratio (PER) than casein, the common standard for comparing the nutritional quality of proteins (34); they are most valuable for medical and pharmaceutical applications (30). The primary proposed use of these proteins is for kidney dialysis patients with dietary restrictions (30). Fraction 2 proteins are used in animal feed (30).

NewAgriculture Inc. is developing a technology for extraction of tobacco protein Rubisco (Fraction 1) to market for non-food industrial uses and will also pursue FDA recognition of the protein as a GRAS (Generally Recognized As Safe) to allow its sale as a food supplement (25).

Pectin: Increasing interest is being seen in the exploration of pectin extraction from tobacco plant cells for use in the chemical, pharmaceutical and/or food industry as a binding agent or filler (35) (36) (37).

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Jyotsna Lal . MBA .Ph.D Chemistry
Professor in Chemistry Department
Christ Church Coplege .Kanpur

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Jyotsna Lal, Ph.D.